

The Development of Graphic Design Online Class Using Thinkific Platform to Improve Commercial Graphic Design Skill

M. Firman Akhsanu Ridho¹, I. Nyoman Sudana Degeng², Nurmida Catherine Sitompul³

^{1,3} Education Technology, Postgraduate, University PGRI Adi Buana of Surabaya

² Education Technology, Postgraduate, State University of Malang

ABSTRACT: This research aims to develop a graphic design online class for adult learners by using Thinkific. The development procedure followed the ADDIE theory that consists of Analysis, Design, Development, Implementation, and Evaluation. The result of feasibility test done by 3 subject matter experts shows that this developed product is feasible to use, rated 96% by instructional design expert, 95% graphic design expert, and 100% by media expert. Finally, the adult learners who joined the online class trial shows a very good response and satisfaction, which means that the developed product is improving their overall learning experience.

KEYWORDS: Online Class, Graphic Design, Thinkific, Adult learner, Commercial Graphic Design Skills

I. INTRODUCTION

Online learning in 2020 has been widely carried out in schools in Indonesia. Besides schools, online learning for adults is also essential to hone particular skills they are interested in. In this case, education for adult students has its own uniqueness. Malcolm Knowles (1980: 43) defines the theory of adult learning or andragogy as a philosophy or analysis of how adults think and how it distinguishes them from kids. It helps to demonstrate how adult learning carries out and to define the right learning types for them. This principle has been established and adopted through the years. This theory arises because adult students tend to attend courses or training related to their work or business for improving particular skills. Therefore, this theory is considered very suitable if applied to the graphic design online class that the researcher will develop.

According to Award (2017: 2), graphic design is a form of visual communication that uses images to convey information or messages as effectively as possible. Award continued that graphic design can refer to the manufacturing process, method of designing, a product produced (design), or even the discipline used (design). Graphic designers employ visual hierarchy and page layout techniques. They also use typography and images to meet specific user needs and focus on presenting elements in an interactive design to optimize the user experience. With the explosion of the internet and the digital revolution in general, a graphic designer's career has taken a big jolt leading to stiff competition for jobs available online.

This is confirmed by a Career Planner survey (2016), which states that graphic designer jobs are projected to grow 5 percent from 2016 to 2026, which is as fast as the average for other work types. Graphic designer jobs will continue to be important in product marketing throughout the economy. Interestingly, graphic designer jobs involving computers and the internet are projected to grow 20 percent over the same period. Global companies are predicted to continue to increase their digital presence and need graphic designers to help create attractive and visually compelling designs.

Unfortunately, graphic design jobs in Indonesia are often associated with Photoshop and high editing skills. Unfortunately, not many people know that numerous alternative apps can help graphic design work easier. Besides, according to the official Adobe website (2020), Photoshop can only run properly with a minimum specification of 8GB RAM and 2GB GPU. This makes graphic design students who have devices under these specifications hampered their creativity.

Therefore, the researchers will develop a learning material about one of the Photoshop alternatives called Canva and how to use it for commercial graphic design. The online class media that researchers have developed will use the Thinkific platform. This media combines video learning and quizzes that can be followed 100% online. Felicia (2019), in her analysis of various popular LMSs, stated that 90% of questions from students at Thinkific could be answered within 5 hours, which indicates that many interactions on the platform can occur within 24 hours. Felicia continued that as an online classroom development tool and online student community, currently, Thinkific has more than 36,000-course creators, 16 million students are registered.

A. Online Class

Online classes are learning activity that is done via the Internet. They have their own peculiarities and can be distinguished from e-learning, web-based learning, and distance learning. The word e-Learning is often equated with online learning. In fact,

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the screening of video programs, which is a digital media group, is included in the scope of e-learning. Likewise, the presentation of lessons through slide presentations also includes e-learning. Essentially, e-learning is a learning process that uses digital electronic media such as multimedia (Prawiradilaga, 2016: 277).

Meanwhile, Web-Based Instruction (WBI) or Web-Based learning is a learning model that utilizes the potential of networks to create learning interactions. For example, online social media is used for interaction, a discussion between students, or students and teachers when the learning occurs (Prawiradilaga, 2016: 275). In his book, Prawiradilaga (2016: 276) continues that Distance Learning (PBJ), or distance learning, often uses material presented in a module format. Delivery of the module is carried out via postal or courier services. Distance Learning can be done by combining more than one form of delivery and delivery of material to students, combining modules with online learning.

Online classes are generally conducted on their own, allowing for greater flexibility in completing the course. Some examples of online courses are MOOCs or Massive Open Online Courses produced by organizations like TedX or Coursera. Many conventional universities offer online courses, including Purdue University through the Kaplan takeover. In online learning, two types of platforms help online learning, namely the Learning Management System (LMS) and the Learning Content Management System (LCMS). LMS was developed to manage the learning process, for example, scheduling lectures, discussions, meeting dates for synchronous patterns, and so on. However, LCMS focuses on processing content or teaching material formed as a core function (Prawiradilaga, 2016: 286). For example, the use of Google Classroom and Moodle technology at the PGRI Adi Buana University Surabaya is part of the LMS. This is because the LMS focus is online class scheduling, teacher management, assignments, etc. While the Thinkific platform used by researchers in this development research is included in the LCMS category because the focus of Thinkific is content delivery or management and presentation of instructional content that is organized regularly so that students can access it easily, sequentially, and can be accessed at any time without time limitation. Apart from Thinkific, major platforms such as Coursera, Udemy, Skillshare, and Teachable are also included in the LCMS.

Thinkific is a website for developing and offering online courses (Capterra, 2020). After the course was designed, the individual may sell or ship it under his own name. Several multinational organizations have used Thinkific to develop educational programs, and it is used in more than 70 nations. One of the key advantages of this program is that the online learning environment can be personalized, and teachers can have payment plans. Setting up courses on this website is quick and straightforward; all the teachers have to do is upload the content they want the students to share. The material can be in the film, PDF, audio, and several other formats. Thinkific allows you to have debates, polls, assessments, and all the different knowledge you need to finish your course.

The Thinkific platform selection is based on the effectiveness of use, cost efficiency, and compatibility with adult learners' learning styles and interactions. This is in line with Felicia's opinion, 2019, which states that as an online classroom development tool and online student community, Thinkific has more than 36,000-course creators, 16 million registered students.

B. Previous Studies

The researchers decided to develop online class because online learning has been proven to help distance learning. Significantly, when Covid-19 has become a global pandemic and forces many students to study at home. Online learning has undergone a lot of research and has even proven to improve students' interest in the teaching material. Wahyuni, Degeng, and Sitompul (2018) developed a thematic teaching material product for teacher companions using the Webbed model. This media is proven valid and worthy of extensive use. Susilo and Suhardi (2018), who conducted online for students, were assessed that teaching materials that utilize Moodle and Office 365 facilities in the tutorial is valid and feasible and does not need to be revised is suitable for wide use. Yulianto, Mustaji, and Sitompul's (2019) research show that the application of web-based flipped classrooms is feasible and applicable. This study's results imply that technology-based learning innovations significantly influence student achievement, and related parties must consider this. Research on the development of online learning applications for blended learning needs conducted by Fatirul (2020) shows that collaboration and communication using smartphone applications can make it more fun and simplify the learning process. Rahayu and Februriyanti (2015) also found that students were highly motivated to take online assessments supported by Facebook group discussions to increase their reading interest. Therefore, it is recommended that online reading skills assessments be undertaken as an additional activity for well-supervised offline reading exams. The research on online learning development conducted by Surahman, Kuswandi, Wedi, Agus, and Degeng (2019) also found a significant result in students' learning experience with "Alams" media. This study aims to develop online learning services that can adapt to students' characteristics in certain learning styles. Based on the results of expert judgment, "Alams" can facilitate the diversity of students. Besides, the learning process can run effectively, as evidenced by the achievement of student learning outcomes that exceed the set targets. Finally, the research conducted by Santosa and Degeng (2020) also agree that the interactive learning approach with mobile computers is more effective in optimizing learning outcomes to address challenges if students are strongly self-regulated.

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II. RESEARCH METHODS

The research objective was to develop an online graphic design class by using Thinkific. It follows the ADDIE model (Molenda,2003) that consists of Analysis, Design, Development, Implementation, and Evaluation.

A. Analysis

According to Degeng (2018: 257), there are 3 kinds of learning analysis processes that need to be done, including:

1) Analysis of the Objectives and Characteristics of Learning Content

The researcher will identify the expected learning objectives. It is mainly to determine the goals of learning orientation: whether conceptual, procedural, or theoretical. This step also serves to determine the supporting objectives that facilitate the achievement of these orientative goals. The learning content characteristics analysis aims to find out what type of material adult students will learn: whether it is in the form of facts, concepts, procedures, or principles.

2) Analysis of Learning Resources

This analysis is carried out after the step of analyzing the objectives and content characteristics of online learning. In this online classroom development research, this step aims to determine what learning resources are available and can be used to convey learning. This activity will be a list of available learning resources that can support the learning process.

3) Analysis of Student Characteristics

The next step is to analyze the characteristics of adult students who will take online graphic design classes. This is done to determine the individual characteristics of students and the characters at their age. Some of which include talent, thinking maturity level, motivation, electronic facilities, internet, and initial abilities. Researchers will conduct a kind of demographic survey to find out these things. The results of this step will be a list that contains the grouping of the characteristics of students.

B. Design

Here, the researchers will decide the learning methods and media. Furthermore, the activity will also consider other means of assistance, such as applicable learning tools, what kind of learning atmosphere, etc. All this is provided in a paper called Lesson Plan. The lesson plan works as a guide for compiling teaching materials included in the development product.

C. Development

The first thing done in product development is to analyze what users can do and what administrators can do on the online class system. Suryani (2018: 143) argues that the Development process in ADDIE includes:

- a. Content development
- b. Selecting and developing supporting media
- c. Developing a guide for students
- d. Developing a guide for teachers,

In this case, the student can access the online class by visiting a particular link made by Thinkific. The guidance for the student is available in both printed and eBook versions. Finally, the teacher's guide will be available on a website that tells them step-by-step instructions to build a similar online class.

D. Implementation

The implementation stage in this study was done by teaching commercial graphic design via Thinkific online class. The students were asked to use Canva as one of the Photoshop alternatives. The researchers choose 10 students from the English Department of Adi Buana University as adult learners who do not have graphic design education backgrounds.

E. Evaluation

The evaluation referred to in the ADDIE Model aims to assess the success of the learning system being developed. It includes the assessments from 3 different subject matter experts and product trials evaluation to the students.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

There are 3 types of results that researchers obtained through this research: (a) The developed online class; (b) Assesments by 3 different subject matter experts and (c) Feedback from the students who joined the online class.

A. The Developed Online Class

The online class is made by using Thinkific LCMS. To access the developed online class, the student needs to visit <https://kelasonlinefirman.thinkific.com/courses/desain-grafis-komersial-dengan-canva>. Over there, the student can access the class and some downloadable material as well.

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Image 1. The online class built in Thinkific

Image 2. The downloadable eBook found inside the online class as a supporting materials

The evaluation is made by the help of Google form. Over there, the students are asked to upload their graphic design work.

Image 3. One of the students' graphic design work

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Finally, the researchers also build a comprehensive guide for those who wanted to develop similar online class. The guide for teachers is available at <https://firmanvoice.com/tutorial-thinkific/>

B. Assessments from Subject Matter Experts

The researchers use 3 subject matter experts to assess the quality of the developed online class product. The instructional design expert assesses the lesson plan, the graphic design expert assesses the teaching material difficulties, and the media expert assesses the quality of media used inside the online class, including the video lesson and written material. The data analysis used is descriptive. The instrument used was a questionnaire for subject matter expert. The analysis is aimed at obtaining the feasibility of developed product to be used as graphic teaching materials.

Table 1. Subject Matter Expert Assessment

Subject Mater Expert	Score (%)	Criteria
Instructional design expert	96%	Very Feasible
Graphic design expert	95%	Very Feasible
Media Expert	100%	Very Feasible

The result of feasibility test done by 3 subject matter experts shows that this developed product is feasible to use, rated 96% by instructional design expert, 95% graphic design expert, and 100% by media expert.

C. Feedback From Students

The students' feedbacks are obtained after the students experiencing the online class and submit the graphic design work as an application task of the online class. The scoring criteria inside the questioner follows the Likert scale below:

Table 2. Likert Scale Used in Student's Questioner Below, the researchers present the feedback scores from the questioners filled by 10 tiral students:

Score	In percentage	Criteria
4	100%	Very Good
3	75%	Good
2	50%	Poor
1	25%	Very Poor

Table 3. The Students' Questioners Report

Feedback Questions	Average Score (%)	Criteria
Have the directions for using the media been clearly conveyed?	97.5%	Very Good
Is the video on each learning activity in the online class interesting and applicable in delivering the material?	92.5%	Very Good
Is the language used in this online class easy to understand?	100%	Very Good
Have the materials in this online class been structured in order?	95%	Very Good
Are the evaluations and the methodology clear enough?	92.5%	Very Good
Are the evaluation questions fit with the material being taught?	100%	Very Good
By using this media, will you understand more about the material?	90%	Very Good
Does this online class make you more excited about creating commercial graphic designs?	87.5%	Very Good
Do you have more curiosity about the material being taught after following this online class?	95%	Very Good
Do you feel the applicable benefits for your daily life?	90%	Very Good
Average of Total Scores	94%	Very Good

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From the table above, we can see that the adult learners who joined the online class trial shows a very good response and satisfaction, which means that the developed product is improving their overall learning experience.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

Based on the development process that has been carried out to produce Graphic Design online class products with the Thinkific platform in learning Commercial Graphic Design for Beginners, it can be concluded as follows:

1. This development produces a product in the form of a Graphic Design online class with a Thinkific platform suitable for adult students. The development process follows the ADDIE (Analysis-Design-Develop- Implementation-Evaluation) development model through five development stages consisting of the analysis stage, the design stage, the development stage, the implementation stage, and the evaluation stage.
2. The feasibility of the online class of Graphic Design with the Thinkific assessed by the Subject matter Experts show very feasible criteria. Furthermore, the students' response in the teaching trial at English Department of Adi Buana University Surabaya to the Online Class of Commercial Graphic Design shows very good response.

Finally, this online class can be a very good supplementary material on a Graphic Design Class for adult learners, or for anyone who wants to learn Commercial Graphic Design at Beginner level.

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